

Career Success: A Campus Placement Recruitment System

Ct Meghna
TLY19CS020
Department of Computer Science
College Of Engineering, Thalassery

Lakshmisandra Ck
TLY19CS028
Department of Computer Science
College of Engineering, Thalassery

Fathima Najaf K
TLY19CS023
Department of Computer Science
College Of Engineering, Thalassery

Sheethal Santhosh
TLY19CS053
Department of Computer Science
College of Engineering, Thalassery

H. A. Nisha Rose
Prof., Department of Computer Science
College of Engineering, Thalassery

Abstract:- Campus hiring is a part of every student's life. Each year, different companies hire freshmen from various colleges. Out of all the passouts that graduate each year, only 3% of them get placed in India. Placements enable the students to interact with industry professionals and kick-start their careers. Nowadays, students choose their colleges according to the past placement results of that college. There is a lot of manual work going into every placement. This work is normally done through social media platforms like WhatsApp. There are many disadvantages and limitations to using WhatsApp as a mode of communication between placement officers and students. In order to overcome this situation, we introduce the "Career Success" application for campus recruitment. The recruitment process is handled by placement officers of respective colleges. This can be very helpful for placement officers as well as students to handle these processes. Placements can be handled through this application with the involvement of three parties, mainly students, a tutor, and a placement officer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Career Success is an android application mainly designed for simplifying the efforts of placement officers. This software contain an admin module , a tutor module and a student module. One of the high responsibilities of any institute is presenting placement opportunities as well as training its college students.

Many problems, like unseen placement drives, importing CV's of shortlisted students to companies, verifying pupil information, uploading university marks of college students ,sending reminders of drives to attend without fail etc. may be resolved through this software. This software can lessen the workload of admins and can also increase the chance of placement at their university. A lot of information like personal info and academic qualifications is saved to be retrieved every time it is wanted. Educational facilities, in addition to interview arrangements, are also furnished to create their abilities and experience many possibilities. Offcampus drives are also part of recruitment, students may be unaware of this recruitment.

Students can also get entry to these hyperlinks to apply via this application. There are many training sites available, but the best one is unknown to the students, so this app will help you focus on high quality tutorials for students. Programming tests are the main problem for many interns; Hence, this app provides daily coding questions with solutions to help them understand the concepts. Many branches have several basic articles; therefore, this application provides a platform for individual learning from other core subjects to help you pass the exams.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

SL NO	AUTHOR & YEAR	ARTICLE TITLE	ALGORITHM/TECHNIQUE	FEATURES	LIMITATIONS
1	Xiangpei Hu , Lirong Wu, Minfang Huang 2011	SMS-based Mobile Recommendation System for Campus Recruitment in China.	semantic matching, tree-based knowledge Matching and SMS-based query matching.	Focuses on profile matching and Preference-list-based two-sided matching.	The system heavily relies on SMS-based interaction, which may not be reliable in areas with poor network coverage or unstable SMS services.
2	J. Vijayan, D. A. Siby and G. P. V. Sabeen 2021	Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Recruitment Process and its Sentiment Analysis	Sentiment analysis to categorize the opinions into “Positive”, “Negative” and “Neutral”.	A sentiment analysis of the data procured is performed to categorize the opinions into “Positive”, “Negative” and “Neutral” from the different stakeholders.	The study may not have taken into account the varying degrees of impact that the pandemic may have had on different sectors, geographic locations, and industries.
3	Animesh Giri , M Vignesh V Bhagavath, Bysani Pruthvi 2016	A Placement Prediction System using k-nearest neighbors classifier	K-nearest neighbors' classifier.	This system predicts the probability of a undergrad student getting placed in an IT company by applying the machine learning model of k-nearest neighbors's classification.	The choice of the k-nearest neighbor's model may not be optimal for predicting job placement.
4	Aishwarya S.Kendle , Mayur S.Nagare, Honey G.Patre 2021	TnP Vision: Automation and Analysis of Campus Placements in Colleges	python backed data analytics, Web Scraping	Focuses on student data management and analysis to digitise practices, providing visibility into students' success, and providing a forum for employers to streamline the hiring process.	Implementing the system may require significant resources and expertise, such as IT staff, funding, and training for users.
5	Sumit jadhav, Gopul Gujar, Ganesh Shinde 2022	Placement Readiness Check	Predicting Placement Status Using Supervised ML Methods.	Students can evaluate themselves about their placement chance and possible package with respect to current preparation.	The predictor system is based on a static model that may not be able to adapt to changes in the job market and industry trends. Therefore, the predictions may become outdated or irrelevant over time.

6	Vivienne J. Wildes & Mustafa Tepec 2008	Influences of Campus Recruiting on Applicant Attraction to Hospitality Companies	This study expands on previous research to further investigate initial reaction to recruiter behavior, during campus interviews.	Applicant perceptions of recruiter behaviours influence applicant attraction, particularly in regards to a perceived interest in candidate and professionalism.	The study focuses only on initial reactions to recruiter behaviour during campus interviews and does not take into account other factors that may affect a candidate's decision to pursue the job.
7	Aseel B.Kmail , Mohammed Maree, Mohammed Belkhatir 2015	An Automatic Online Recruitment System Based on Exploiting Multiple Semantic Resources and Concept-Relatedness Measures.	semantics-based models are used.	An automatic online recruitment system that employs multiple semantic resources to highlight the semantic contents of resumes and job posts.	Incompleteness of semantic resources, Limited domain coverage.
8	A. B. Kmail, M. Maree and M. Belkhatir 2015	MatchingSem: Online recruitment system based on multiple semantic resources	Automatic semantics-based online recruitment system	Statistical-based concept-relatedness measures to alleviate the problem of semantic knowledge incompleteness in the exploited resources.	The system heavily relies on existing semantic resources, which may not cover all possible keywords and concepts that could be relevant to job matching.
9	Lu Shumin and Rao Yuan 2010	Research on Campus Recruitment management platform based on dynamic electronic commerce	dynamic electronic commerce.	In order to solve the deficiency about existed employment management system, a core business scenario is proposed in the paper for the whole process of employment, which includes five roles, such as government, enterprise, university, students, and platform administrator	The effectiveness and suitability of the proposed model may be limited to the specific context of China, and may not be applicable or generalizable to other countries or regions.

III. EXISTING SYSTEMS

Searching for a placement opportunity and receiving notification of a company's placement drive will be made possible by the student module and the company module. Currently, the placement officer is in charge of the college's placement drive. He must manually send the notification of the planned drive via WhatsApp. Every time a new company arrives at the campus, he has to send a Google form to the students to fill out. Some students may have forgotten to apply or may not have received the placement drive notifications. Students fill out the application form without reading it. As a result, there is no way to change the application form. Training resources are not always available for the student to prepare with. They must search Google for materials. Currently, students must upload a CV to the company, but the CV will be in a different format, and the company may not be able to view it.

Technical issues may be tough to understand during the placement exam, which will be addressed by a significant number of students. To learn more about a specific student, an admin must contact or message someone in a group. Students have no awareness of any off-campus drives, such as their packages or information about the company; to find out, they must use Google and have the placement officer send them an off-campus drive over WhatsApp. When students apply for job opportunities, they occasionally provide incorrect information, but the placement officer has no way of knowing if it is correct. So we added a tutor module to our system to verify the students' information. As a result, the placement officer is under a great deal of work pressure. Furthermore, students find the task difficult to deal with during placement drives.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEMS

The application aims to provide a more efficient and user-friendly approach by allowing students to upload their information directly, reducing the workload for placement officers who normally have to collect and give the data manually. The system will also offer automated notifications to students as reminders to notify them regarding the date of the drive. Another key feature is that the placement officers will be able to easily sort and submit student information to relevant companies according to the company's requirements, such as backlogs, CGPA, and branch. The system will also offer an option for providing training materials that help students better prepare for job interviews and other placement-related tasks and improve their coding skills. In addition, the system will display off-campus and on-campus options in different categories, making it easier for students to filter and find relevant placement opportunities. There are three modules that we are introducing in our app: student, admin, and tutor. For students, the system provides a simple, user-friendly interface that enables them to register themselves, manage their profiles, update their profiles, and upload their CV. CVs

will be generated in a uniform format so that all students' individual CVs look similar. They can also view training materials so that they can improve their skills in coding, for interviews, etc. They can contact administrators with any questions or concerns they may have. Also, they can view company details and filter them according to their preferences. Shortlisted students list will be available along with time and date of next round. For administrators the system offers an easy-to-use interface that enables them to give reminders to the user to stay on top of the deadline. They will upload the training materials to the users. They can view students' details and sort according to those details. They will provide company details to the users as off-campus and on-campus options. Furthermore, they will send the students' details to the company via mail. Additionally, they can view department-wise bar charts to get the placement results.

The spot registration option is provided by the admin on the date of the drive to enable registration for those students who are in that location at that time. For tutors, the system enables them to verify students' IDs, update semester marks, view the drive result, and filter out the students. The students who have created faulty accounts with fake information will be rejected by the tutor. After the rejection, students will not be able to log in again without prior permission.

V. CONCLUSION

The project is beneficial for placement officers as well as students. This application can facilitate better communication between students, tutors, and the placement officer, leading to more placements in college. The application helps the students build their profiles, and they can update their details whenever required. The system provides a user-friendly approach to the students' learning as well as their application processes. On-campus and off-campus drives are shown separately. Students who are unaware of placement drives will be able to learn about them through this application. Training materials will be very useful for improving the areas of improvement for the students. The application will be helpful for other branches like ECE, EEE, Civil, etc. to learn some of the IT subjects. The admin sorts each student's details, and after getting permission from the students, the admin directly exports them to the respective companies. Tutor will verify the student's ID and update their semester marks; this helps to ensure that the information in the app is accurate and up-to-date. This application enhances the college placement and career of its students.

REFERENCES

- [1]. X. Hu, L. Wu, C. Li and M. Huang, "SMS-based Mobile Recommendation System for Campus Recruitment in China," 2011 10th International Conference on Mobile Business, 2011, pp. 152-157, doi: 10.1109/ICMB.2011.30.
- [2]. J. Vijayan, D. A. Siby and G. P. V. Sabeen, "Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic on Recruitment Process and its Sentiment Analysis," 2021 2nd International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication, Embedded and Secure Systems (ACCESS), 2021, pp. 270-273, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS51619.2021.9563327.
- [3]. A. Giri, M. V. V. Bhagavath, B. Pruthvi and N. Dubey, "A Placement Prediction System using k-nearest neighbors classifier," 2016 Second International Conference on Cognitive Computing and Information Processing (CCIP), 2016, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/CCIP.2016.7802883.
- [4]. A. S. Kendle, M. S. Nagare, H. G. Patre, R. S. Zanwar, V. G. Kottawar and P. B. Deshmukh, "TnP Vision: Automation and Analysis of Campus Placements in Colleges," 2021 5th International Conference on Computer, Communication and Signal Processing (ICCCSP), 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICCCSP52374.2021.9465519.
- [5]. S. Jadhav, G. Gujar, G. Shinde, S. Shivane and D. S. Jadhav, "Placement Readiness Check: Predicting Placement Status Using Supervised ML Methods," 2022 2nd International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT), 2022, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/CONIT55038.2022.9847863.
- [6]. Vivienne J. Wildes & Mustafa Tepeci (2004) Influences of Campus Recruiting on Applicant Attraction to Hospitality Companies, *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 2:1, 39-51, DOI: 10.1300/J171v02n01_03.
- [7]. A. B. Kmail, M. Maree, M. Belkhatir and S. M. Alhashmi, "An Automatic Online Recruitment System Based on Exploiting Multiple Semantic Resources and Concept-Relatedness Measures," 2015 IEEE 27th International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI), 2015, pp. 620-627, doi: 10.1109/ICTAI.2015.95.
- [8]. A. B. Kmail, M. Maree and M. Belkhatir, "MatchingSem: Online recruitment system based on multiple semantic resources," 2015 12th International Conference on Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD), 2015, pp. 2654-2659, doi:10.1109/FSKD.2015.7382376.
- [9]. Lu Shumin and Rao Yuan, "Research on Campus Recruitment management platform based on dynamic electronic commerce," *The 2nd International Conference on Information Science and Engineering*, 2010, pp. 4663-4666, doi: 10.1109/ICISE.2010.5690003.